
→ “Make it TZ, take it T-easey”

MESS 0009

The T-ease (TZ) brand in EPEMC

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ABSTRACT

The following is merely branding discussion for the EPEMC *electro* series.

Keywords: Plasma - electricity - magnetism - electromagnetism - geology - meteorology - comets

Designing the Paradigm Shift

In SPACERS and AIM standards, there is an emphasis on leverage. Therefore, for the most part, we encourage scale, repetition (and refinement), and utility or function over art. However, in a brand, which does have an effect upon the success of any endeavor, we seek to create simple standards for rapid scale and growth. It is proposed, to the community, that a simple T-EZ (or just TZ) approach is taken to create a T-ease of reading and almost scrabble-like cross-threading.

EPEMC L E C T R O G E O L O G Y	E L E C T R O M E P E M C T E O R O L O G Y	E L EPEMC C T R O C O M E T S
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Etc.

The “T” shape has ties to Gobekli Tepe, as well as the *tarun* glyph, which is, of course, related through many plasmaglyphic systems to the thunderbolt, and the /|/, the secret name for God (IAO). The T-ease of this lays in the layout, but also the a) ease and b) promise/visual tease created by the negative space. Lots of forms of cross threading can come into play, or there can be a visual layout/juxtaposition.

This may seem stupid, or pedantic, but actually there are some reasons for a TZ banner, listed off to the side of a work. For example there is the sword dual cosmological meaning: the comets were also known as weapons of the gods, or even gods themselves, and as such have powerful weaponized value in the cultural DNA. Just like swords.

Or, consider the cross motif. The relationship of the divine to weather is long established, and commonly referred to in mass media, myth, and religion, as well as business branding. Therefore, it might be worthy to consider functional layouts which drive towards the use of “Christian” and “maltese/celtic” motifs. This standard - in the meaning of the word for banner or brand - can be used for sidebars, menus, etc.

Conclusion

No replies are sought, or needed, it is a free concept for the public to utilize at their leisure.